

POLARITY OF MOLECULES IN RELATION TO THEIR ADSORPTION
BY CHARCOAL

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Opinions vary as to the influence of polarity of the adsorbate molecules and also that of the solvent used, on the adsorption of substances by activated charcoal. The present work was carried out with a view to throwing light on some of these controversial points. Effect of introducing different polar groups on adsorption was evident from the following series: $C_6H_5COOH > C_6H_4(OH)COOH$ and $CH_2ClCOOH > CH_3COOH$, $CH_2(OH)COOH > CH_2NH_2COOH$ —chloro group has a tendency to increase the adsorption, while both OH and NH_2 groups decrease it, the effect of the amino being greater. Effect of specific grouping into a benzene ring was studied with compounds like $C_6H_5NH_2$, $C_6H_5(OH)$, C_6H_5COOH , and $C_6H_4(OH)COOH$ in different media like H_2O , $CHCl_3$, C_6H_6 with the result: $C_6H_5NH_2 > C_6H_5(OH)$, $C_6H_5COOH > C_6H_4(OH)COOH$ (H_2O medium); $C_6H_5(OH) > C_6H_4(OH)COOH$, $C_6H_5COOH > C_6H_5NH_2$ (both in $CHCl_3$ and C_6H_6). Comparative study of adsorption of the individual compounds in these media reveals that the adsorption decreases in the series: $H_2O > C_6H_6 > CHCl_3$, except in the case of phenol, the order being there $H_2O > CHCl_3 > C_6H_6$ —strictly the order of decreasing polarity of solvent molecules.

Modern trend of research on adsorption by activated charcoal lies in studying the importance of the polarity of solute and solvent molecules on adsorption. Work so far done in this particular line, however, shows differences both as regards actual observations and their interpretations. The more important of these discrepancies are enumerated below:

(i) According to Schilov and NeKrassov (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 65) the substitution of most radicals for hydrogen, except hydroxyl and sulphonic groups, increases the adsorption but Bartell and Miller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1106) and Linner and Gortner (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 35) are of opinion that carboxyl and NH_2 groups also like OH group decrease adsorption to a marked extent.

(ii) Contrary to the observation of Platonov, Bergman and Salman (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 62, 1975), Schilov and NeKrassov (*loc. cit.*) recorded that the *trans* form of compounds possessing a double linkage is more strongly adsorbed than the *cis* form.

(iii) Contrary to the observations of Sata and Kurano (*J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1932, 53, 617; *Kolloid Z.*, 1932, 60, 137; cf. Tamamushi, *Chem. Abs.*, 1931, 25, 5606), Jermolenko and Levina (*Acta Physicochim. U.S.S.R.*, 1939, 10, 451) as also Heymann and Boye (*Naturwissen.*, 1930, 18, 157) conclude from their results with mixed solvents that the relation between adsorption and dipole moment of the solvent is antipathic.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to throwing light on some of these controversial points.

Experiments have been done on the following subjects:

I. The effect of different polar groups in adsorbate molecules on the adsorption keeping the solvent constant;

(a) adsorption of fumaric acid and maleic acid to show the effect of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers;

- (b) adsorption of acetic acid, monochloroacetic acid, glycollic acid and amino-acetic acid to show the effect of introducing chloro, hydroxyl, and amino radicals into a molecule of acetic acid ;
- (c) adsorption of benzoic acid and hydroxybenzoic acid (salicylic acid) to show the effect of OH group in an acid molecule ;
- (d) adsorption of phenol, benzoic acid, salicylic acid and aniline in different media to compare the effect of introducing a specific group into a benzene ring.

II. The effect of polarity of the solvent on the adsorption properties of charcoal.

Benzene has been chosen as the non-polar solvent, chloroform as moderately polar solvent having the dipole moment 1.15D ; and water as highly polar solvent having dipole moment 1.8D.

Adsorption isotherms of acetic acid, monochloroacetic acid, benzoic acid, phenol, aniline, and salicylic acid in water, chloroform and benzene media have been recorded.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Activated Charcoal.—Purest variety of sugar available in the market was charred in a silica basin and ignited at a low red heat to drive off the greater part of volatile matter. The charcoal was reduced to granules in an agate mortar, repeatedly digested with concentrated HCl and washed at first with distilled water to free it from HCl, and then with equilibrium water till the conductivity of the wash liquid remained unaltered. It was dried and powdered in an agate mortar. Activation was effected by heating to 900° for 6 hours at pressures between 1 and 2 mm. of Hg. It was then stored free from contamination in a stoppered bottle in a vacuum desiccator containing KOH sticks.

The specific gravity of the charcoal, thus prepared, was measured by the liquid displacement method using benzene and the specific surface by dye adsorption method due to Paneth *et al* (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 101, 480 ; *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 1215) and Bachmann and Briger (*Kolloid Z.* 1926, 39, 342) using methylene blue. The charge on charcoal particles was determined by electroendosmotic experiments in a U-tube using platinum electrodes.

Adsorption of substances was determined by shaking in a mechanical shaker for 5-6 hours 0.5 g. of charcoal in 50 c.c. solution. It was kept overnight inside a thermostat maintained at 28°, filtered rapidly, rejecting the first few c.c and an aliquot part of the filtrate titrated with NaOH using suitable internal indicators. For phenols and aniline, bromide-bromate titration was used. Sørensen method ("Biochemical Laboratory Methods for students of the Biological Science," by C. A. Morrow and W. M. Sandstrom, 1935 Ed., p. 127 ; *cf.* Sørensen, *Biochem. Z.*, 1907, vii, 45, 407) of titration adding some formaldehyde before titration was utilised in the case of the amino-acid. Adsorption data have been expressed in terms of millimoles of substances adsorbed per g. of charcoal.

Nature of Charcoal.—The charcoal used had a soft velvety black appearance. The following data give an idea about its nature and characteristics

Ash content.	Density	Specific surface.	Charge.
0.284%	1.58	10.5 sq. m	0

It will appear that the ash content of the sample is not so low (0.01%) as used by Miller and his co-workers (Bartell and Miller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1866; 1923, **45**, 1106); but in view of Kolthoff and van der Goot's observation (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1929, **48**, 265) on samples of charcoal having ash content 1.15% and also sample purified according to the method of Miller (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 1031) with ash content near about 0.01% the higher ash content in the former case does not appear materially to influence the nature of the adsorption isotherm and also as there is practically no reaction between the solute and the impurities in the charcoal, it is unlikely that it will affect in any way our relative and comparative measurements.

The charge of the charcoal particles, as determined by electro-osmotic experiments, is zero here. In previous works there are also references of charcoal having a negative charge (Sasaki, *J. Biochem. Japan*, 1927, **8**, 102; Acharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 723), the nature and amount of charge depending mainly on the process of preparation of activated charcoal. In the face of these observations it is not unlikely that the charge due to impurity might have balanced the opposite charge due to the charcoal itself resulting in a neutral variety of charcoal in this case. From the study of adsorption of basic dyes by the negatively charged charcoal particles, Sasaki (*loc. cit.*) concludes that mass attraction between charcoal and dye molecules is the chief cause of adsorption which is undoubtedly slightly assisted by electrical attraction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Different Polar Groups in Adsorbate Molecules

(a) *Adsorption of fumaric acid and maleic acid in aqueous medium.*—The results of adsorption of fumaric and maleic acids by activated charcoal at 28° are given in Table I. c_1 denotes the initial concentration (i.e. concentration before adsorption), c_2 , the equilibrium concentration (i.e. concentration after adsorption) and x/m , the millimoles of substances adsorbed per g. of charcoal.

TABLE I

Fumaric acid			Maleic acid		
c_1	c_2	x/m	c_1	c_2	x/m
0.7485N/10	0.6630N/10	0.427	0.750N/10	0.679N/10	0.355
0.5988	0.5154	0.417	0.600	0.5324	0.338
0.4491	0.3690	0.400	0.450	0.3839	0.33
0.1994	0.2221	0.386	0.300	0.2452	0.275
0.1497	0.0874	0.311	0.150	0.1081	0.21

The results tabulated above show (on plotting) that maleic acid (the *cis* form) is less adsorbed than the fumaric acid, the *trans* form of the compound. This result while corroborating earlier observations of Schilov and NeKrassov (*loc. cit.*) and Linner and Gortner (*loc. cit.*) seems to contradict the observations of Platonov, Bergman and Salman (*loc. cit.*).

(b) *Adsorption of acetic acid, monochloroacetic acid, glycollic acid and amino-acetic acid in aqueous medium* by activated charcoal at 28° are given in the following tables and are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

TABLE II

Acetic acid			Monochloroacetic acid		
c_1	c_2	x/m	c_1	c_2	x/m
1.426 N/10	1.365 N/10	0.61	1.44 N/10	1.371 N/10	0.69
1.1408	1.084	0.56	1.152	1.085	0.67
0.8556	0.8061	0.49	0.864	0.799	0.65
0.713	0.6673	0.45	0.576	0.5187	0.573
0.5704	0.5284	0.42	0.288	0.2415	0.465
0.2852	0.2507	0.34			

TABLE III

Glycollic acid			Amino-acetic acid		
c_1	c_2	x/m	c_1	c_2	x/m
1.416 N/10	1.389 N/10	0.27	1.396 N/10	1.382 N/10	0.14
1.1328	1.106	0.268	1.1168	1.104	0.128
0.8496	0.8258	0.238	0.8376	0.8265	0.111
0.7080	0.6856	0.224	0.5584	0.5491	0.093
0.5664	0.5455	0.209	0.2792	0.2710	0.082
0.2832	0.2683	0.149			

(c) Adsorption of benzoic acid and salicylic acid in aqueous medium by activated charcoal at 28° are given in Table IV and is graphically represented in Fig. 2.

TABLE IV

Benzoic acid			Salicylic acid		
c_1	c_2	x/m	c_1	c_2	x/m
0.3477N/10	0.3055N/10	0.4222	1.434 N/100	1.166 N/100	0.268
0.2782	0.2384	0.3977	1.1462	0.8895	0.2657
0.2086	0.1721	0.3653	0.8604	0.6125	0.2479
0.1391	0.1031	0.3598	0.7170	0.4765	0.2405
0.0695	0.0374	0.3211	0.5731	0.3540	0.2191

Comparative study of the adsorption (Tables II, III and Fig. 1) in aqueous medium shows that the adsorption decreases in the order: $\text{CH}_2\text{ClCOOH} > \text{CH}_2\text{COOH} > \text{CH}_2(\text{OH})\text{COOH} > \text{CH}_2(\text{NH}_2)\text{COOH}$. The introduction of a Cl group has a tendency to increase the adsorption, while both hydroxyl and amino groups decrease it, the effect of the 'amino' group being greater than hydroxyl group. Linner and Gortner (*loc. cit.*) as also Bartell and Miller (*loc. cit.*) recorded that the adsorption of succinic acid, malic acid, tartaric acid and aspartic acid decreased in the order: succinic acid > monohydroxy-succinic (malic acid) > dihydroxysuccinic (tartaric acid) > aminosuccinic acid (aspartic acid). Bartell and Miller also showed that though acetic acid was appreciably adsorbed, the adsorption of amino-acetic acid was practically nil.

Lowering of adsorption due to the introduction of a hydroxyl group is further shown in the comparative adsorption of benzoic and salicylic acid (Table IV and Fig. 2), the results being in accordance with those of Kolthoff and Van der Goot (*loc. cit.*) and Bartell and Miller (*loc. cit.*). The latter workers recorded that adsorption decreased in the series: benzoic > salicylic acid > *o*-aminobenzoic acid. Improvement of adsorption

due to the introduction of a chloro group finds its indirect support in the conclusion derived by Schilov and NeKrasov (*loc. cit.*) that the substitution of most radicals except hydroxyl and sulphonic groups increases the adsorption.

(d) Adsorption of phenol, aniline, benzoic acid and salicylic acid by activated charcoal at 28° in media having different polarities :

TABLE V

Phenol in H ₂ O			Phenol in C ₆ H ₆			Phenol in CHCl ₃		
c ₁	c ₂	x/m	c ₁	c ₂	x/m	c ₁	c ₂	x/m
1.3843N/10	1.314 N/10	0.7032	1.34 N/10	1.302 N/10	0.190	0.0485N/10	0.0124N/10	0.180
1.1079	1.04	0.6788	1.072	1.035	0.185	0.7588	0.7213	0.187
0.8308	0.7675	0.833	0.804	0.7947	0.05	0.5691	0.5255	0.218
0.5530	0.4933	0.8064	0.536	0.513	0.115	0.3794	0.3428	0.183
0.2770	0.2304	0.466	0.268	0.2495	0.095	0.1897	0.1676	0.110
0.1385	0.0980	0.4049						

TABLE VI

Aniline in H ₂ O			Aniline in C ₆ H ₆			Aniline in CHCl ₃		
c ₁	c ₂	x/m	c ₁	c ₂	x/m	c ₁	c ₂	x/m
2.069 N/10	1.996 N/10	0.73	1.362 N/10	1.340 N/10	0.06	2.921N/10	2.928N/10	..
1.6552	1.586	0.60	1.0896	1.080	0.05	2.336	2.333	..
1.2414	1.169	0.72	0.8172	0.814	0.016	1.753	1.756	..
0.8276	0.7572	0.70	0.5448	0.5555	..	1.168	1.165	..
0.4138	0.3482	0.66	0.2724	0.2727	..	0.584	0.582	..
0.2069	0.1506	0.50						

TABLE VII

Benzoic acid in H ₂ O	Benzoic acid in C ₆ H ₆			Benzoic acid in CHCl ₃		
	c ₁	c ₂	x/m	c ₁	c ₂	x/m
<i>Vide</i> Table IV	0.484 N/10	0.4645N/10	0.0975	0.4154N/10	0.3992N/10	0.081
	0.3872	0.3687	0.0925	0.3323	0.3186	0.0685
	0.2904	0.2763	0.0705	0.2492	0.2395	0.0485
	0.0968	0.0907	0.0305	0.1662	0.1573	0.044
				0.0831	0.0782	0.0243

TABLE VIII

Salicylic acid in H ₂ O	Salicylic acid in C ₆ H ₆			Salicylic acid in CHCl ₃		
	c ₁	c ₂	x/m	c ₁	c ₂	x/m
<i>Vide</i> Table IV	1.393 N/100	1.266 N/100	0.064	1.92 N/100	1.811N/100	0.054
	1.1144	0.994	0.060	1.536	1.443	0.047
	0.8358	0.7306	0.053	1.152	1.071	0.041
	0.5572	0.4811	0.038	0.768	0.6988	0.0345
	0.2786	0.2269	0.026	0.384	0.3221	0.031

(e) *Adsorption of acetic acid, monochloroacetic acid by activated charcoal at 28° in benzene media*: (For results in H₂O medium, see Table II).

TABLE IX

c ₁	Acetic acid in C ₆ H ₆		c ₁	Acetic acid in CHCl ₃		x/m
	c ₂	x/m		c ₂	x/m	
1.763 N/10	1.678 N/10	0.43	1.637 N/10	1.580 N/10	0.285	
1.4104	1.322	0.44	1.3096	1.269	0.203	
1.0578	0.983	0.37	0.9822	0.9436	0.193	
0.7052	0.6443	0.31	0.6548	0.6189	0.179	
0.3526	0.3137	0.195	0.3274	0.3028	0.123	

TABLE X

Monochloroacetic acid in C ₆ H ₆			Monochloroacetic acid in CHCl ₃		
c ₁	c ₂	x/m	c ₁	c ₂	x/m
1.4395N/10	1.354 N/10	0.430	1.6662N/10	1.615 N/10	0.256
1.1576	1.077	0.373	1.1108	1.070	0.204
0.8637	0.7927	0.355	0.5554	0.5284	0.135
0.5758	0.5148	0.305	0.4443	0.4207	0.12
0.2879	0.2473	0.203	0.2222	0.2066	0.078

On plotting the tabulated results of adsorption (x/m against c_2 from Tables V-VIII) of phenol, aniline, benzoic acid and salicylic acid in water, benzene and chloroform media separately, three adsorption isotherms have been obtained showing the effect of specific grouping in the benzene ring in different media as follows:

Aniline > phenol > benzoic acid > salicylic acid in H₂O medium (Fig. 2)
 Phenol > salicylic acid > benzoic acid > aniline in C₆H₆ medium } same order
 Phenol > salicylic acid > benzoic acid > aniline in CHCl₃ medium }

When similarly related compounds are compared, it is found that aniline is better adsorbed than phenol (*cf.* Kolthoff and Van der Goot, *loc. cit.*) and benzoic acid better than salicylic acid (*cf.* Bartell and Miller, *loc. cit.*) in aqueous medium. In non-polar benzene medium and also in moderately polar chloroform-medium, the order is just reversed.

Phenol > aniline, and salicylic acid > benzoic acid

This seems to show that the more hydrophilic solute is adsorbed more strongly by charcoal in a more hydrophobic medium and *vice versa* (cf. Freundlich and Weller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2228). The marked lowering of adsorption of benzoic acid in benzene medium may also be partially attributed to its association in that medium, thereby decreasing the number of particles striking the charcoal surface at a time and increasing the size of the particles, perhaps to such an extent as may cause difficulty in their entering the ultra pores of the charcoal surface. When the adsorption of an individual compound like acetic acid (Fig. 4, Table IX), monochloroacetic acid (Fig. 3, Table X), benzoic acid (Table VII), phenol (Fig. 5, Table V), aniline (Table VI) and salicylic acid (Table VIII) in these three media is compared, a general relation holds good (except in the case of phenol) as follows: $\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{C}_6\text{H}_6 \cong \text{CHCl}_3$. The difference in adsorption values between C_6H_6 and CHCl_3 as media is small in majority of cases, those in C_6H_6 being slightly greater.

The difference would have been probably still smaller, had there been no experimental error due to evaporation of the readily volatile CHCl_3 , in spite of adequate precautions—a fact which might have raised the value of c_2 , resulting in a slightly lower value for $c_1 - c_2$ or x/m than the theoretical. However, neglecting the adsorption in chloroform it is found that the adsorption is greater, the greater the polarity of the solvent which is in accordance with the observations of Sata and Kurano (*loc. cit.*). Jermolenko and Levina (*loc. cit.*) and, Heymann and Boye (*loc. cit.*) however, are of opinion that the relation between adsorption and dipole moment of solvent is antibatic. The slightly lower adsorbability in chloroform medium instead of being greater, as was expected, than that in benzene medium may be explained on the basis that in this particular case, perhaps, the secondary factors like lowering of surface tension and solubility (Freundlich, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 57, 385; Santa, *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 49, 275; de Izagurre, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry", *Eng. Ed.*, 1926, 817) which affect the adsorption are so prominent as to overshadow the single primary effect of polarity of the solvent. If, however, the adsorption isotherms of compounds in chloroform and benzene media only are compared, the antibatic relation as obtained by Heymann and Boye, and Jermolenko and Levina seems to hold good. Extensive work in this line can only settle these controversial points.

CONCLUSION

1. Fumaric acid (*trans* form) is better adsorbed than maleic acid (*cis* form).
2. Introduction of a hydroxyl group decreases the adsorption. Amino group affects the adsorption in the same way but to a greater extent. Chloro group has a tendency to increase the adsorption as is evident from the following series :

Benzoic acid > salicylic acid

chloro-acetic acid > acetic acid > glycollic acid > amino-acetic acid (effect of introducing chloro, hydroxyl and amino group to a molecule of acetic acid).

3. Adsorption isotherms of benzoic acid, salicylic acid, phenol and aniline have been compared to show the effect of specific grouping in a benzene ring. Polar influence of the solvent has been studied by using solvents like benzene, chloroform and water.

H_2O medium—*aniline* > *phenol* > *benzoic acid* > *salicylic acid*

CHCl_3 „ —*phenol* > *salicylic acid* > *benzoic acid* > *aniline* (practically zero)

C_6H_6 „ —*phenol* > *salicylic acid* > *benzoic acid* > *aniline*

When the adsorption of an individual compound in these three media is compared, a general regularity holds good except in the case of phenol in that the adsorption decreases in the series : $\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{C}_6\text{H}_6 > \text{CHCl}_3$. Only in the case of phenol the relation is $\text{H}_2\text{O} > \text{CHCl}_3 > \text{C}_6\text{H}_6$ which is strictly the order of decreasing polarity.

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